

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M 2.1. Knowledge Exchange about Each Aquifer and Main Groundwater Issues, Existing Datasets and Further Needed Monitoring in Each Case Studies

VERSION 0.2

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The current document reports the milestone M2.1 which summarizes groundwater status, data availability and design of an innovative High-Resolution Monitoring Approach (HRMA) for each case study considering its characterisation, historical data and emerging problems. This milestone is part of Task 2.1 entitled “**Implementation of an innovative high-resolution monitoring**”. The preparation of M2.1 has also benefited from the gathered information and inputs from Task 4.1 “**Systems characterisation, stakeholder mapping and governance analysis**”. A first impression of the specific groundwater status in the Mediterranean region (MED) is presented using Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis. Then, a summary on groundwater status, data availability and design of HRMA for each case study is reported.

1. Groundwater SWOT Analysis in the MED Region

Identification of the most important groundwater problems in the MED region. To this end, Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis regarding quantitative and qualitative groundwater aspects will be carefully investigated

Focusing on the scope of WP2 related to data sharing, analysis and applications, a SWOT analysis (Table 1) has been made taking into account the gained insights while doing the WP2, literature review as well as the inputs and experiences from the other members of the consortium regarding data management and sharing.

Table 1. Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis regarding quantitative and qualitative groundwater aspects for the MED region.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All countries have some form of groundwater level monitoring infrastructure and scheme, • A few of the countries and subnational provinces in the MED region have very advanced databases for groundwater quantity and quality, allowing for transparent analysis and data sharing, • Existing of long-term groundwater quantity and quality data with a different spatiotemporal resolution, • Considerable knowledge production about groundwater status and budget in Euro-MED countries driven by European reporting policy, • Comprehensive and straightforward water policy in the Euro-MED countries, • Presence of systematic monitoring and data sharing policy in the Euro-MED countries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sharing of groundwater quantity and quality is lacking for most of the countries, • Long term data about groundwater abstraction rates are scarce if existing, • Most representatives of groundwater-based agriculture and environmental concerns have no access to groundwater level data in a majority of the MED countries, hindering transparency of groundwater management and public participation, • Unequal economic, institutional and knowledge capacities to develop sustainable groundwater management in the region, • Contrasting funding for research and scientific-based management options, • Absence of groundwater monitoring standards and data dictionary among the MED countries, • Groundwater extraction in North Africa is met increasingly by non-renewable groundwater sources.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is an increased interest towards the establishment of sustainable groundwater use in the MED region, • National policies to homogenize and concentrate groundwater quality and quantity data, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The complex interplay of climatic, geologic and human factors around the MED region make it a particularly vulnerable area, • Increasing water demand in the whole region has been translated into higher rates of groundwater extraction, often beyond the replenishment capacity,

- Combining in-situ data-driven analysis, regional modelling, and increasingly available remote sensing data can open new horizons for groundwater assessment in data-scarce regions such as the MED region,
- Increasing of international and national research funding programs for water management during the last decades covering the monitoring, assessment and implementation aspects,
- Participatory management through social learning space opportunities are crucial to accelerate public engagement and awareness towards groundwater sustainable development,
- Existing of successful Groundwater Management with trend reversal (e.g. La Mancha aquifer in Spain), which can be used as a success story for other regions,
- Other seas governance structures and their environmental management history can be a source of inspiration for the MED sea region,
- As many countries in the south and east of the MED are more dependent on groundwater, raising awareness about its importance might be more straightforward.
- Climate change impacts are more severe in the MED compared to other regions,
- Large differences in political and legal framework among neighbouring MED countries,
- Groundwater is a hidden resource, and its status and impacts aren't apparent compared to other water bodies,
- Existing of the large share of Transboundary Aquifers in the southern MED region with intensive use but characterised by low to very low operational management levels,
- For most countries in the South and East end of the MED, groundwater is the main source of water, or at least of domestic water use, making them more vulnerable to depletion,
- Current implementation of more efficient irrigation systems may not lead to absolute water savings, as more water demanding crops are being made for a higher profit in water-scarce regions.

2. Groundwater Status in Each Case Study

A summary on groundwater status, data availability and if HRMA is needed for each case study is reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of the five case studies and their key groundwater problems considered in InTheMED project. P and T refer to Precipitation and Temperature, respectively.

Characteristics	Requena-Utiel, Spain	Tympaki, Greece	Castro Verde, Portugal	Grombalia, Tunisia	Konya, Turkey
Size (km ²)	1360	55	30	363	62000
Population	30,000	25,000	7,276	201,836	~3,000,000
Location	Inland	Coastal	Inland	Coastal	Inland
Mean P & T (mm y ⁻¹ / °C)	440/13	500/15	567/16	356/20	387/12
Principal groundwater users	Agriculture, urban	Agriculture	Urban, mining	Agriculture, industry, tourism	Agriculture, urban
Overexploited	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
groundwater pollution	No	Nitrate, salinity	Mine waste	Nitrate, salinity, (COD in punctual hotspot area)	Nitrate, salinity
Historical groundwater level data (time extend and frequency)	Number of wells: 17 Period: 1981-2021 ^a , Frequency: Monthly sampling	Number of wells: 5 Period: 4/2004-9/2008 Frequency: Random (1-3 months until 2006 and monthly until 2008)	Number of wells: 19 Period: from 08/1996 to 03/2021 Frequency: Irregular ^b ,	Number of wells: 34 Period: 1972-2019, The period depends on the implementation of piezometer in the well ^c . Frequency: 2 sampling campaigns/year.	Number of wells: 100 Period: Earliest monitoring well was installed in 1966, Frequency: Monthly.
Historical groundwater quality data (parameters, time extend, frequency)	Number of wells: 12 Period: 2008-2020 ^a Frequency: Annually Parameters: Nitrates, Alkalinity, Bicarbonates, Calcium, Carbonates, Iron, Zinc, Aluminum, Total organic carbon (TOC),	Number of wells: 5 Period: 4/2004-9/2008 Frequency: Random Parameters: pH, Electrical Conductivity and Water temperature	Number of wells: 19 Period: from 04/1977 to 03/2021, Frequency: Irregular ^b , Parameters: the most monitored parameters are Ammonia, Chloride, Dissolved Oxygen,	-	-

	Chlorides, Copper, Electrical conductivity at 20 °C, DDT, Fluorides, Magnesium, Nitrates, op'-DDD, op'-DDE, Pesticides Directive 75/440 / CEE Minimum Sum, Total Pesticides, Potassium, Dissolved oxygen saturation, Sodium, Sulfates, Redox potential, Xylene		Electrical Conductivity, Nitrate, Sulphate and pH.		
HRM Sensors	Planned installation of two sensors (OTT ecoLog 1000 (Dilus) or VEGAWELL 53 (VEGA)) - water level and temperature.	-	Not yet. This was planned but with the pandemics was postponed.	3 Aqua Troll 500 sensors (Water level, Temperature, Nitrate and Dissolved Oxygen)	8 Keller DCX-22 (sensors measure water level, electrical conductivity and temperature. Managed and operated by DSI (State Water Works))

^a Period varies greatly from one well to another.

^b Depending on the station, the measurement frequency is usually biannually, annually, or just a single observation for the entire period (from 1 to 51 observations).

^c 9 Wells (1972-2019), 2 Wells (1974-2019, 1975 -2019), 2 Wells (1985-2014), 1 Well (1991-2018), 3 Wells (1995- 2008, 1995-2010, 1995-2019), 4 Wells (1999-2014, 1999-2017, 1999-2018, 1999-2019), 2 Wells (2001-2018), 4 Wells (2002-2012, 2002-2015, 2002-2015, 2002-2019), 1 Well (2003-2018), 3 Wells (2004-2008, 2004-2018, 2004-2019), 2 Wells (2005-2015, 2005-2019) and 1 Well (2006-2019).